

SACRED MEANINGS AND SILENT STRUGGLES: RELIGIOUS COPING BY WOMEN IN DISSATISFIED MARRIAGES.

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ABSTRACT

Pakistani women frequently experience marital dissatisfaction as a result of sociocultural constraints, unequal relationship labor, and emotional neglect. Religion may become the dominant coping mechanism in these situations, but how women interpret religious coping in unhappy marriages is unexplored. Twelve religiously devout married women (aged 25–40; married for at least two years) who self-reported persistent marital conflict participated in semi-structured interviews using an Interpretative Phenomenological Methodology. Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis (IPA) was used to analyze the data. The results reveal a painful discrepancy between Islamic marriage ideals and experienced reality, as well as ongoing emotional loneliness. Religion served as a dual coping mechanism: while negative coping increased guilt, self-silencing, and prolonged endurance through constrictive interpretations of *sabr* (patience) and gendered expectations, positive coping (such as prayer, dhikr, and meaning-making) offered solace and emotional control. The study expands upon Pargament's Religious Coping Theory (1997), emphasizes how joint-family pressures, socially mediated religious messages, and the role of religious leaders influence coping outcomes, which can either support women's rights or reinforce silence.

keywords: Religion, Coping, Dissatisfaction, Faith, Pakistani women.

INTRODUCTION

One of the greatest social institutions in any given society is marriage; though, at the same time, marriage can be a stressor and a source of instability. Empirical evidence indicates that, in a higher percentage of married couples, women report being less satisfied in the marriage than men, mainly due to social demands, unequal division of labor, and unmet emotional and psychological needs (Jackson et al., 2014). This kind of dissatisfaction in women leads to negative psychological conditions, such as stress, depression, and poor life satisfaction (Whisman, 2014; Amato, 2010). Based on these observations, there is a need to understand the process by which women cope with their lives when they are not satisfied with their marital relationships.

Religious coping is an eminent process whereby people deal with life stresses and it entails using faith, spiritual conviction, and religious customs (Pargament et al., 2000). Women in societies with high religious orientations tend to seek help through prayer, religious ceremonies, and spiritual interpretations (Fallahchai, 2021). Empirical data show that some positive religious coping mechanisms, including seeking spiritual support, framing marriage as a religious institution, and participating in joint prayers, help reduce stress and lead to greater marital satisfaction (Jenkins et al., 2021; Lai et al., 2023). Negative religious coping, which includes spiritual dissatisfaction, religious guilt, and the belief that marital problems are a form of divine punishment, on the other

hand, increases distress, does not lead to better marital outcomes (Pargament et al., 2011; Pollard et al., 2014).

Although the research confirms the importance of religious coping in determining the outcomes of marriage, several gaps remain. To begin with, most of the studies are placed in Western settings with little research in South Asian, Middle Eastern or predominantly Muslim societies where religion is a huge part of marriage. Second, there is a lack of literature that focuses specifically on women as the target group, even though the same results have been replicated over time: women express more dissatisfaction. Third, there is not much known regarding the role of negative religious coping in long-term marital dissatisfaction in women, which is a promising field to explore further.

Despite the considerable amount of research that has been conducted to find out the role of religion in the life of a family, relatively little empirical research has been done on how women, particularly, use religious coping mechanisms in situations where they are not satisfied with their marriages. The studies of this interrelation are necessary because of the gender specificity of marriage role and the key impact of religion on coping mechanisms. The knowledge of the role of religious coping by women in marital dissatisfaction can guide pastoral and marital counselling and culturally competent therapy. This study therefore aims to contribute to the literature on marriage, religion, and women's psychological well-being by examining the relationship between women's religious coping and marital dissatisfaction.

1. Research Questions

1. What are the determinants of women who continue, compromise, or dissolve unsatisfactory marital relationships?
2. What is the impact of religious coping and women's independence, self-identity, and long-term marital outcomes?

2. Literature Review

Marriage is generally viewed as the primary source of security, intimacy, and emotional support. However, it is also shown that women express more marital dissatisfaction than men do (Jackson et al., 2014). Gendered expectations, imbalances in the allocation of domestic labour, lack of emotional bonding, and sociocultural influences on family

breakage are among the factors leading to this phenomenon (Whisman, 2014). Constant dissatisfaction has been linked with negative psychological effects, such as anxiety, depression, and poor quality of life (Amato, 2010). Since women tend to play leading caregiving and relation roles, they become especially susceptible to the psychological consequences of marital strain (Perrone-McGovern et al., 2015). It therefore becomes urgent to explain how women experience and manage marital stress.

The role of religious coping strategies in the processes of marriage has received considerable scholarly attention. It has been indicated that negative religious coping is linked to more marital distress, and positive religious coping is linked to more marital satisfaction. Indicatively, Pollard, Riggs and Hook (2014) found that couples who used collaborative religious coping exhibited better adjustment than those who used negative coping styles. On the same note, Fallahchai (2021) established that positive coping strategies increased marital happiness when marriage was viewed as sacred.

In a meta-analytic study, Jenkins et al. (2021) found that the effects of religious coping on marital love trajectories differ between men and women, suggesting a moderating effect of gender. The relational dimension of coping in marriage, as further supported by Lai (2023), found that both actor and partner effects were present in positive and negative coping strategies concerning marital satisfaction. Such results suggest that religious coping influences the quality of marriage in general and personal adjustment in particular.

Women tend to adopt religion as a coping tool more than men do in societies with tried religious beliefs that are very ingrained in the cultural norms (Mahoney, 2010). Religious coping may provide women with a psychological strength and sense of meaning when faced with marital dissatisfaction coupled with communal support (Fallahchai, 2021). On the other hand, religious coping that is maladaptive, like the interpretation of a marital conflict as a Godly punishment, can instead worsen the psychological distress of the women (Pargament et al., 2011).

Religious coping and its interaction with marital functioning among Muslim societies is a relatively new but developing research field. Despite the possibility of gender and religiosity differences, research in Iran and other Muslim settings

indicates that sanctification and desirable religious framing are linked to both partners adapting to marriage (Fallahchai et al., 2021). It is imperative to mention that the facilitation of adaptive coping in comparison to the promotion of the negative dynamics is conditional upon the culturally and doctrinally particular interpretation, including the conceptions of patience and marital duty (Fallahcha, 2025).

Empirical research in Pakistan is scarce, but promising, and directly attributes marital dissatisfaction by women to religious coping. The more Pakistani Muslim respondents were religious and engaged in religious practice, the higher their marital satisfaction (Aman et al., 2019), which suggests a protective role of religion in the quality of marriage in that setting. The presence of strong cultural norms that organise the agency of women in marriages is also reflected in other Pakistani research on sexual and reproductive health, marriage conflict, and help-seeking. Such studies suggest that, in certain circumstances and adopted coping mechanisms, religious coping can contribute to the resilience of women and prevent them from seeking help or abandoning unsatisfactory marriages.

However, there are relatively less studies that specifically look at religious coping in women who are not content in their marriages. In most studies, the gendered elements of coping have been sidelined to the extent of marital adjustment or couples in general. It is imperative to know that women have a unique approach to religious coping because they often encounter marital unrest differently because of cultural, emotional and relationship demands.

3. Theoretical Framework

The religious theory: Pargament Religious Coping Theory (1997).

The Religious Coping Theory by Pargament (1997) can serve as a strong starting point for explaining how women manage the challenges of marital dissatisfaction in religious-oriented societies. It is a theory that explains how people tap into religious beliefs, practices, and spiritual significance in response to stress, and thus why these coping strategies can be helpful to some but cause an increase in emotional distress for others. The theoretical lens used in the current study helps understand the significance of religious coping in motivating women to persist, negotiate, or end

difficult marriages, and the role of faith in relation to self-identification, affective well-being, and future marital success.

Emotional neglect, unfair allocation of duties, and lack of satisfaction of psychological needs often result in marital dissatisfaction among women. Religion is a salient coping mechanism in cultures where the religious identity is part and parcel of the marital roles and expectations. This fact is directly confirmed by the framework proposed by Pargament (1997). He argues that whenever people become overwhelmed, helpless or any form of emotion, they are inclined to turn to religious beliefs, rituals, and spiritual meanings as a tool of coping. This is a situation that is faced by most women in troubled marriages: a lack of social support, strong cultural pressure to keep the relationship alive, and lack of avenues to express dissatisfaction. As a result, Pargament's (1997) theory provides a conceptual framework for understanding why women turn to prayer, Qur'an recitation, *sabr* (patience), spiritual reinterpretation, and support from the religious community as the main strategies for coping with marital stress.

The theory will be applied to positive religious coping, including seeking spiritual reassurance, praying to find guidance, or affirming marriage is a sacred trust, which have the ability to provide psychological sustenance to the women during difficult marital conditions. Pargament (1997) explains that positive religious coping (PRC) implies a safe connection with the supernatural and produces positive redefinitions of stress. On the other hand, the theory presents the negative religious interpretations, such as the interpretation of marital problems as religious punishment, the religious guilt of the aspiration desires, or the belief that it is religiously condemnable to pull out of the marriage. Pargament (1997) summarizes these constructs into negative religious coping (NRC), which is normally occasioned by fear, shame, spiritual confusion or punitive conceptions of God.

This theoretical paradigm is quite relevant to the objectives of the study because it sheds light on how religious coping influences women to tolerate, bargain or find their way out of unhappy marriages and how religious moderates their free will, identity, and future wellbeing. The reliance of the analysis on the framework by Pargament (1997) would make possible a fine, learned explanation of

the multifaceted and rather conflictual contribution of religion to the marriage experience of women.

3.1 Model of Theory

Theory integrated Conceptual Model of Marital Dissatisfaction: Religious Coping Theory (Pargament, 1997)

4. Research Methodology

The methodological foundation for the current study, which examines marital discontent and religious coping among married Pakistani women who observe religious beliefs, is described in this section. The study's qualitative research design, underlying interpretivist stance, phenomenological approach, research setting and participant characteristics, purposive sampling strategy, interview-based data collection procedures, Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis (IPA) techniques, methods to improve trustworthiness, and ethical considerations are all described. This methodology's goal is to guarantee openness and show that the study's goals, the meaning-centered philosophical underpinnings, and the qualitative design used to record women's lived experiences and faith-based coping mechanisms within the Pakistani sociocultural context are all clearly aligned.

4.1 Philosophical Worldview

The study was based on an interpretivist worldview, which holds that people's lived experiences, interpretations, and interactions within specific cultural settings socially construct reality (Schwandt, 2023). According to this viewpoint, religious coping and marital discontent are subjective experiences rather than fixed, universal phenomena. In accordance with this philosophical

stance, the researcher aimed to comprehend how religiously devout Pakistani married women interpreted their experiences through Islamic marriage standards to make sense of marital suffering. This interpretivist approach aligns with the study's qualitative design and phenomenological methodology, enabling a thorough investigation of how women interpret their discontent and how religion may serve as both a source of solace and a source of restriction in their marriages.

4.2 Research Design

The research design that was used in this work was a qualitative phenomenological research design aimed at examining the experiences of Pakistani women who use religious practices as a coping mechanism in their marital relationships that are not satisfying. The choice of phenomenology is based on the fact that it provides a systematic approach to comprehending the ways people make sense of everyday experiences, thus it agrees with the purpose of the study to explain the complex and subjective reality of women who encounter relational problems (Clandinin and Connelly, 2000). The research recreates the participants' narratives by using the structural elements of setting, plot, activities, climax, and conclusion. This research design is most suitable when

investigating the experiential aspects of religious coping and marital discord and it will help in offering an in-depth, interpretive examination of how the participants enumerate meaning to their religious engagements in alleviating marital strain. In this regard, IPA was used (Smith, Flowers and Larkin, 2009).

4.3 Data Collection

Participants were recruited in a way consistent with purposive sampling strategies for sensitive research issues through community-based informal networks and referrals. The inclusion criteria included the following: (a) married women aged between 25 to 40 years; (b) married at least two years; and (c) self-reported marital conflict and willingness to share their experiences. This sample size of 12 women met these requirements and is within the recommended sample size of IPA, which states that small cohorts are required so that the sample can be analyzed in depth. Also, due to the saturation level, no new data were collected. These data were gathered by semi-structured interviews based on an interview schedule that sought to elicit them to elaborate on (a) marital dissatisfaction and marital strain; (b) how religious beliefs and practices had served to alleviate the situation (reactively or proactively); (c) how they felt that this had impacted their agency, self-concept and choice making (e.g., endurance, negotiation or exit); and (d) their experiences of seeking religious advice (e.g., through family elders or scholars).

The semi-structured format was applied to promote consistency among participants and to provide flexibility to probe meanings, contradictions, and critical junctures. The interviews were conducted as a closed environment, which was established by participants or in a secure online format, of which the participants were not made aware of it. Informed consent was obtained during the conversations so that they could be transcribed and further analyzed. Field notes were retained to allow the researcher to capture interpretive richness; it was necessary to record contextual observations, including tone of emotion, pauses, emphasis, and the researcher's first impressions.

4.4 Data Analysis

The analysis technique was Interpretive Phenomenological Analysis (IPA). It was an analytic process that proceeded using typical IPA steps (1) repetitive reading of each transcript to

achieve an immersive familiarity; (2) initial marking of the descriptive and linguistic and conceptual observations; (3) formation of emergent themes of each case; (4) sorting the themes into overarching categories by identifying conceptual liaisons and patterns; and (5) transitioning to the subsequent cases but retaining the idiographic focus, and then synthesizing across cases to identify common themes and areas of divergence. Such a method allowed this piece of research to discover convergence, similarities among participants, and nuance, meanings that are individual in particular situations and religious meanings. All the participants gave informed consent as well as the researcher interviewed them in full accordance with the ethical principles. The audio tapes were accepted and transcribed verbatim. The process of transcription was very time-consuming, yet the authenticity of the participants' voices and the ability to provide an interpretation of the data had to be valid. After transcribing the interviews, IPA was applied to each one to identify first-order themes, which portray each participant's personal experience and perception; second-order sub-themes, which represent personal patterns and meanings relative to the whole dataset. These themes were subsequently synthesized and matched to the available literature to generate theoretical knowledge.

4.5 Ethical Considerations

The dynamics of the research process and all the work were conducted ethically, and the principles of research were followed; the anonymity of the participants was also ensured, and sensitive sources were handled carefully. The authors of the study made it clear that participation was voluntary and that the participants had the right to stop it at any time. Having been informed and consenting to participation, all the procedures are in accordance with the relevant institutional ethical standards. The respondents were informed about the purpose of the study, the research method, their anonymity, and their freedom to withdraw without adverse effects. To comply with ethical research practice, verbal consent from all participants was sought before data collection to ensure their participation was knowledgeable and voluntary.

Table 1: Raw Data, Themes, and Analytical interpretations

Raw Data / Codes (Interview Excerpts)	First-Order Themes (Participant Terms)	Second-Order Themes (Researcher Interpretations)	Theme Generation (Aligned With IPA Analysis)
“My marriage feels like living with a polite stranger... we are not enemies, but we are not partners either.” (P1)	Feeling emotionally disconnected	Emotional loneliness rooted in unmet relational needs	Emotional Loneliness & Invisibility
“Marriage is supposed to bring tranquility; I don’t feel that.” (P4)	Ideal vs reality of Islamic marriage	Sacred marital expectations intensifying dissatisfaction	Discrepancy Between Islamic Ideals & Lived Reality
“Culture ignores true Islamic teachings... joint family ruins marital privacy.” (P7)	Conflict between Islam and culture	Cultural norms undermining religious marital ideals	Cultural Distortions of Religious Marriage Norms
“Tahajjud is the only place where I can pour my heart out... it gives me emotional strength.” (P12)	Relief through prayer	Positive religious coping as emotional regulation	Religion as Source of Solace & Resilience
“A good woman does sabr... I felt sinful for being upset.” (P5)	Misinterpretation of sabr	Religious messages reinforcing self-silencing	Harmful Religious Narratives & Self-Blame
“My husband uses religion to demand his rights but ignores his obligations.” (P6)	Religious manipulation	Weaponization of religious discourse to maintain control	Religious Authority as a Control Mechanism
“A scholar told me Islam forbids harm... that changed everything.” (P3)	Religious validation	Religious reinterpretation empowering boundary-setting	Faith-Based Empowerment & Justice-Oriented Coping

Table 2: Socioeconomic Profile of Participants

S.no	Respondent Number	Gender	Age	Occupation	Education	Time of Marriage (years)	No. of Children (If any)
1	Participant 1	Female	24	Student	MS	2	0
2	Participant 2	Female	32	Teacher	M.Sc.	6	2
3	Participant 3	Female	35	Housewife	Matric	8	3
4	Participant 4	Female	28	Tutor	BA	4	1
5	Participant 5	Female	38	Housewife	MA	5	3
6	Participant 6	Female	27	Student	MS	3	1
7	Participant 7	Female	34	Teacher	Mphil	10	4
8	Participant 8	Female	36	Housewife	FA	7	3
9	Participant 9	Female	31	Doctor	BDS	2	1

10	Participant 10	Female	35	Baker	BS	4	2
11	Participant 11	Female	30	Housewife	MS	6	3
12	Participant 12	Female	30	Teacher	M.Sc.	3	1

5. Data Analysis

The current research paper began with a review of answers received following in-depth interviews with religiously inclined married women in Pakistan who stated that they were dissatisfied with their marital relationships. The analytic agenda was more concerned with the determination of recurrent thematic patterns in relation to the antecedents of dissatisfaction, like, failures in communication, unmet emotional needs, conflict patterns, and pressures in family or personal ties, and how the participant framed these experiences in a religious context. Using the Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis (IPA) research team, selected an extensive thematic coding and pattern identification to generate cross-participant similarities and individual meanings hidden in the personal accounts. Analytical focus was explicitly placed on religious coping styles that include prayer, Quran recitation, patience (sabr), dependence on faith (tawakkul), seeking advice with religious leaders, and instances of spiritual distress, and the aim was to determine the impact that such practices may have regarding emotional regulation, decision-making and response to conflicts. This integrative analytic approach helps understand religious coping as both a source of support and limitation, thereby determining the persistence of women, negotiation strategies, and mental health within the Pakistani sociocultural context.

5.1 Gendered burden and emotional loneliness.

The results suggest that emotional loneliness is more than an individual affectivity experience, but a social construction of expertise founded on Pakistani socialized gendered marital norms. This kind of emotional detachment is supported by the social norms which assume that wives should maintain family harmony, absorb conflict, and put the needs of their family before their own affective needs. As a result, marital loneliness is a patterned phenomenon in society, present and coexisting with physical proximity but lacking emotional visibility, and, at the same time, it places responsibility for maintaining the relational emotional climate on the woman.

Religious coping was an intentional, frequently used practice among the twelve women involved and was shaped by individual religiousness and the sociocultural environment, which often obscures marital issues. To many of the participants, religious practice served as internal refuge when faced with unfulfilled emotional demands. It allowed them to redefine hardship as a god-imposed ordeal, the rejection of all hope, and the maintenance of personal respectability. Interviews indicate that, although marriages seemed to be stable, in terms of no blatant abuse or divorce, most of the interviewees said that there was great internal emotional emptiness.

Several respondents explained how their spouses were physically but not emotionally available. One of the respondents described her experience in marriage in the following statements:

"My marriage is like living with a friendly stranger. We are neither enemies nor we are partners... We continue to stay under the same roof, even share meals, but there is no connection whatsoever (P1)."

On the same note, another participant explained that the relationship became less warm and more emotional:

"I would term our relationship as functional but not very emotional at this point. We share a home, we share, we share, but the emotional closeness, the warmth that we shared during the initial years, is lost. (P 2)."

In line with the above narrations, the participants used to describe marital living whereby there is lack of affective connectivity even though they are living together, hence describing an existence that is seemingly fulfilling but devoid of inner substance that is indicative of unfulfilled expectations. Emotional neglect is associated with a sense of invisibility and guilt about sharing desires that are perceived as extending beyond the simple provision of material sustenance.

As (P11) explained:

"There are times when I feel lost as a woman. It seems as though I am being whittled away. And then there is guilt. I always ask myself-am I too much? (P 11)."

The thoughts of the respondents highlight the fact that religion is not only a personal belief system but also a socio-culturally relevant coping mechanism that acts proactively in defining, experiencing and

reacting to marital dissatisfaction amongst religiously aware Pakistani women. The empirical evidence also indicates that religious coping is also interwoven with gendered expectations and structural restrictions and as such, plays a role in the ambivalent and complex manner in the agency of women.

The other interviewee expressed the following position:

"Now we are in a polite but unsatisfying relationship. We do not quarrel much, however, we are not attached very much... Affectively, I am lonely despite being married. (P 8)"

The other participant stated:

"Emotionally, I feel drained. I usually wake up nervous, finding ways of surviving the day... I have trouble sleeping; I am always in my mind about what I should say or not say to maintain the peace at home. (P 9)"

Emotional dissatisfaction was expressed strongly by participants. The described marital relations were not abusive as such, but showed a significant lack of the much-desired emotional bonding, which created an internal emotional disarray. This mental health was impacted negatively by this emotional discontent, as evidenced by the quotes above, leading to energy drainage, which impaired the performance of everyday chores. Women with this condition worked hard to avoid further conflict in their lives.

Women talked about crying at night, insomnia, and fatigue that affected work and raising children: *"Sometimes I seem to be the one shouldering the burden of the house, as he is just there by my side, physically. Not emotionally, not mentally" (P 1)."*

According to these stories, gendered expectations of endurance and emotional work are some of the factors that aggravate dissatisfaction in marriage, whereby women are required to uphold peace in the household, manage their distress, and redirect unmet needs to avoid an explosion or judgment. The theme in general is to emphasize the role of emotional loneliness as a structure and relational state of being, which is molded by cultural constructs of womanhood and marriage, rather than just an emotional condition.

5.2 Ideal marriage and lived dissatisfaction on the part of the Muslims.

This analysis indicates that Pakistani married women who religiously adhere to their religion use it as a main framework of coping during marital dissatisfaction as it provides them with emotional

comfort, moral guidance and socially acceptable means of enduring and coping with distress. The women always applied an Islamic perspective to their marriages and referred to the Quranic ideas regarding specialties as a cloth (libaas) and marriage as a source of sakinah (tranquility). This reflects the concept of sanctification of marriage.

This was well noted by one of the participants (P4): *"What I was taught is that marriage is a mercy, a partnership and half of one's faith. Husband is meant to be his wife, and wife his husband-to cover, to soothe, to respect each other... Due to that, my marriage is not what it should be. I do not find that peace that I read about. (P 4)"*

Participant also believed in the same belief system where she was taught that marriage is a relationship where both partners owe each other some duties and obligations. However, since there is a gap between what she was taught and what the picture shows, it does not make sense to her, and that is indeed disappointing.

Another respondent reflected the same gap between ideal and experience:

"Marriage is meant to be a comfort, and a love and mercy, as I have heard.... Comparing this description to my reality, I believe something is missing. (P 6)"

Based on the above quotes, it is evident that marriage is not simply a contract but a feeling of companionship, care and honour. Certain women clearly pointed at the conflict between faithful Islam and cultural Islam. One participant commented:

"I believe my religion gives much importance to the connection between husband and wife it is madness how our culture disregards the actual religion and its directives on the life of the couple and their privacy and turns marriage into a family affair. The cultural demands literally destroy the way an Islamic couple is supposed to live. (P 7)"

In the quote provided above it is clear that there is a disparity between what the religion is preaching and what is actually happening. As mentioned above, religion indeed places significance in the relationship between husband and wife. Conversely, the culture disregards that and instead promotes the joint family system, which destroys the couple's privacy. On the one hand, religion is discouraged, but on the other hand, culture tends in the same direction. They are both contradictory to one another. The religious teachings and the societal demands are at extremes. When one

attempts to establish a connection, it creates conflict in the ideologies.

Equally, one of the participants, whose husband had taken a second wife, reported conflict between doctrine and practice.

“Islam does permit a man to marry more than one wife under the conditions of justice, however, justice is not only about money but also about emotions. I am aware that he did not sin by remarrying. In his turn, I believe he has dealt with it in a manner which is not compatible with our religion, regarding fairness and kindness. (P 5)”

The respondent clearly admits that a marriage of more than one wife is religiously acceptable, yet she also analyses the scenario using the ethical state of Islam as justice in which she cautions that although it might be sufficient, the manner in which the act is being done still goes against the ideals of Islam as a form of fairness and mercy. Justice is composed of emotional fairness that women consider marital experiences in relation to sacred marital ethics, not merely of legal allowances. Stated otherwise, the discontent is not only due to the husband's remarriage, but also to a perceived lack of kindness, consideration, and responsibility in relationships, and to the reality that fails to conform to what she believes Islam teaches about justice and human decency.

The theme in a nutshell is that religiousification of marriage can not only reinforce devotion but also increase suffering in the moments when religious beliefs are violated. It is even more unbearable when sacred ideals are used to compare intimate life and set the standards.

5.3 Religion as a two-sided coping tool.

The theme represents the key contradiction of the participant testimonies: religion acted as a mental health crutch and a possible limiting factor in the scenario of marriage dissatisfaction. Religious coping turns out to be a two-sided phenomenon in this study, as it can safeguard well-being by providing comfort, hope, and moral support; it also fosters self-silencing or long-term sustenance when religious meaning is associated with blame, stigma, or one-sided marital expectations. This duality is in line with empirical evidence that religious coping has both positive and negative effects on psychological adjustment depending on the nature of coping adopted and those meanings that have been placed on stress.

5.3.1 Positive religious coping - solace, meaning, and resilience.

This sub-theme underscores the importance of positive religious coping as a major channel participants used to manage emotions and psychological endurance amid marital dissatisfaction. Women reported on faith-based practices and beliefs to hold on to hope, rebuild inner peace, and re-form a meaning where the marriage relationship seemed to be emotionally unsafe or unsatisfying. Their stories describe coping styles generally interpreted as positive: seeking spiritual assistance, benevolent religious re-evaluation (seeing hardship as a test and a source of wisdom), and a cooperative attitude toward God that fosters a sense of strength rather than helplessness.

Tahajjud was sought as an emotional outlet: (P 12).

“During Tahajjud, I address Allah as though he is really listening to me. Sometimes I cry during dua. That is the only place I can give it all... They help me survive. They provide me with the emotional strength.”

Late-night prayer was also mentioned by another participant as the most helpful strategy:

“The most helpful are the night prayers that occur when it is late. Now I am able to spill out everything to Allah without being judged. Although the situation may not improve, I feel lighter in my heart. (P2)”

These passages depict positive religious coping as an emotion-regulation and resilience-enhancing approach to the reality of marital dissatisfaction. Both participants define Tahajjud and dua as rituals, but also as a close, relational space where they can feel heard, accepted, and secure, requirements they feel are not fulfilled in the marriage. The diction of pour my heart out and without being judged are indicative of the fact that the concept of a late-night prayer is one of some confessional release and emotional release and venting, a psychologically secure release of distress. Meanwhile, the excerpts reveal that the advantage of prayer does not necessarily depend on some immediate external alteration of the situation (Even if the problem doesn't change), but on the inner change-a change of feelings, judgments and perception of power (my heart feels lighter, they help me survive).

A Sufi-infused background (P 8) explained the grounding effect of dhikr and dhikr circles:

“Dhikr is the most grounding. It takes me back to the given moment and relaxes my nervous system. The dhikr classes particularly help me remember that I am not only

a wife and a mother, but I am also a soul on a journey to Allah. (P 8)"

The participant clearly connects dhikr with the control of the body, and remembrance can be seen as an emotion-oriented coping mechanism that lessens arousal, anxiety, and overwhelm, which is especially vital in the background of persistent marital dissatisfaction.

In general, the descriptions that fall into this sub-theme indicate that positive religious coping served as a stabilising force on which the women were able to cope with the emotional distress, decrease loneliness and maintain a sense of dignity in the face of marital dissatisfaction. Tahajjud, dua, Qur'an recitation, dhikr, and attendance of dhikr circles allowed people to feel that they were supported spiritually, that they were getting emotional, that they were getting calm internally, even when their marriage situation was not immediately improved. These stories explain how religious coping with positivity provided emotional control, meaning, and dignity, which are related to greater adaptation.

5.3.2 Negative and ambivalent religious coping - guilt, self-blame, and spiritualized endurance.

Although most respondents referred to faith as a comforting factor, this sub-theme portrays more painful and inhibitory means through which religion also influenced their handling of marital dissatisfaction. Spiritualized endurance was frequent in this work when the meaning of sabr was treated as a restrictive idea of passive endurance, as women went to an extent of rationalising emotional neglect, downplaying harm, or staying in a circuit of self-withholding to maintain marital stability and social respectability. This sub-theme thus points to the ambivalence of the religious coping: the very religious structure, which provides meaning and hope, may, under some interpretations and social demands, be turned into a process that reinforces dissatisfaction by moralizing the position and transferring responsibility to the assumed inadequacies of the woman, to the relational injustice or unexpressed rights.

The ambivalence was implicitly recorded by one of the participants:

"Both better and worse. Better, as I believe that without faith I would be incredibly depressed. Worst still, in a sense that there are times I remain in unhealthy habits

longer since I convince myself that doing so will mean I failed in Islam in some way. (P 7)

(P 5) explained internalising messages which equated piety to silence:

"My mother had always said, a good wife keeps the home neat. A good woman does sabr.'... This is what I found guilty about my desire to have an emotional connection. I began to feel as though I was the sinful one to be angry. (P 5)"

These quotes demonstrate the two-sidedness, the duplicity, of religious coping, and how it can become a source of power and a tool of limitation. It is explicitly illustrated through participant: faith helps her to maintain her mental health, but at the same time, it becomes a source of distress by redefining the role of agency as a spiritual failure. In that regard, religion is a coping mechanism as well as a moral evaluative system, one that can stabilise emotions and raise the psychological cost of conceiving change. The second quotation demonstrates that negative coping is frequently socially transmitted and gendered to occur by constructing family messages to equate ideal womanhood with silence and endurance: A good wife keeps the home intact... does sabr. In this case, sabr is not presented as the patient's brevity of having limits, but rather as self-suppression and restriction of valid emotional desires.

Women were also morally at cross crossroads regarding their dissatisfaction:

"I feel guilty of being dissatisfied. I reason, 'At least I have a spouse who earns and does not hit, other women have worse. then that feeling has its close upon my feelings sometimes.'" (P 8)

This quote indicates that the participant is experiencing a negative/ambivalent form of religious coping whereby she is coping with marital dissatisfaction by engaging in downward comparison and guilt-based self-regulation. By reminding herself that her husband is not abusive or does not provide her with anything, she redefines her distress as either non-existent or unthankful, which subsequently turns off emotional expression. Instead of assisting her in the dissatisfaction processing, this coping mechanism acts as self-silencing, reducing the amount of her own unmet emotional needs, and discouraging her to think about relational inadequacies. This would explain how women absorb social and religious norms that a good wife must be grateful and patient, even when stripped of emotional comfort, in your research.

Some women mentioned how husbands would use religious language to coerce them into obedience, particularly in relation to sex or silence. For example, (P 6) noted:

“My husband had statements such as, it is haram to refuse me my rights, when he speaks of intimacy; therefore, he employs religion to excuse his demands. but he seldom speaks of his own obligations in a religious point of view.” (P 6)

This quote is an example of how religion is transformed into the locus of authority and framing of moral selectivity in marital conflict. The participant reports how her husband used religious terms haram to deny me my rights to approve his demands in terms of intimacy, without considering the Islamic call on mutual responsibilities, benevolence, and morality. This shows the interpersonal religious struggle, in which religious discourse is not perceived as reassuring or guiding, but rather, it is an instrument of pressure, guilt, and conformity.

Overall, this sub-theme proves that religion was not necessarily a safe and protective tool; to a number of participants it also turned out to be a moral pressure system that further aggravated suffering and extended the unhealthy patterns of relations. Negative or ambivalent religious appraisals in these accounts facilitated coping where faith minimized the depression and provided a sense of meaning but on the other hand, increased endurance through fear, shame, and increased responsibility on the woman.

5.4 Passive sabr to justice oriented faith.

This motif reflects one of the most critical changes in the meaning-making of participants over the years: most women had initially understood sabr (patient waiting) as quiet submission, putting up with emotional abandonment and not complaining, as well as making marital stability more important than their own pain. This kind of passive sabr was frequently supported by family guidance, societal norms and religious teachings about obedience and preserving the household in the Pakistani sociocultural environment. Consequently, sabr at times was made a spiritualized self-silencing extending discontent and postponing boundary-setting.

In the case of (P 5), this change was the heart of her subsequent parting with a husband who physically abused her:

“Long time I was struggling to adjust my reality in a religious pattern of meditation and adherence to rules. I believed that a good Muslim lady perseveres. During the early years, I did not understand the concept of religious patience and I suffered longer than I should. However, later, a further insight into Islam and its emphasis on justice and protection, in particular, served as an impetus to leave”. (P 5)

Such passage sums up the main development of the theme by following a distinct change of religious evaluation of marital sufferings by the participant. First, she has expressed her interpretation of religion within a very limited perspective of patience and obedience, where to be a good Muslim woman was equated with patience. Sabr is a spiritualized self-silencing in this phase, a style of coping that would promote harm acceptance and action delay even when suffering is harmful. This is an indication of the way religious coping can be limiting when religious significances are associated with feelings of guilt, moral failure insecurities, or inflexible gender requirements. However, as time passes, the participant talks of a profound re-evaluation particularly on its focus on justice and protection.

Likewise, (P 3) started to make more assertive claims about her rights:

“My conviction that Allah is just has compelled me to demand my financial matters more. I have informed my husband, Fear Allah and spend fairly, you will be questioned about this. I never used to talk that way before, I was too shy.” (P 3)

This quote explains how justice-inspired faith may be turned in the practical agency of marriage. Instead of religious silence to silence herself down, the participant resorts to one of the fundamental theological doctrines of Allah is just to support her claims of fairness and to rebrand her self-advocacy as a religiously-based action. The fact that her abacus has changed to too shy to talk to telling her husband fear Allah indicates transition to passive endurance to rights-based moral assertion when religion comes in as a source of confidence, language, and authority to delimit boundaries.

Even those women who remain in their marriages noted that they moved out of the strictly self-sacrificial explanations. (P 6) reflected:

“Now I start to realize that Islam does not request women to forget about themselves. Patience does not imply that one tolerates emotional abuse. Sabr is not to be self-destructive; he is not meant to be dignified.” (P 6)

This passage is an indication of a critical re-definition of sabr and a breakpoint in the religious meaning-making of the participant. Instead of defining patience as silence, self-denial, and emotional suppression, she outlines a subtle meaning: Islam does not ask women to put themselves in the background and patience does not demand becoming a witness of emotional abuse.

To sum up, this theme represents one of the essential developmental changes in the religious coping of participants: most women shifted their interpretation of sabr as silent endurance and self-denial to a more justice-related, dignity-related vision of Islam. At the beginning of their marriages, limited interpretations of patient and obedience frequently extended emotional injury by undermining the establishment of boundaries and explaining suffering as an indicator of piety. However, with time, more knowledge and reflection about religion allowed women to reevaluate distress on the basis of Islamic values of being just, responsible, and not subjected to harm, giving them an opportunity to seek rights, establish boundaries, and, in certain situations, abandon harmful conditions without abandoning faith.

5.5 Community, religious leaders and silence, validation and control.

This theme examines how the coping paths of participants were highly influenced by external religious and social authorities, specifically, the role of religious leaders, elder, and community norms that stipulated what is a desirable Muslim marriage and a good wife. To most women, going to religious counsel was not only a religious endeavor but also a societally relevant approach to achieving clarity, legitimacy, and direction in an environment where marriage dissatisfaction is commonly stigmatized and where personal suffering is normalized.

5.5.1. Support of silence and forbearance.

This minor theme reflects the participants' experiences of religious and communal advice that framed marital dissatisfaction as an issue to be quietly endured, rather than discussing it through mutual responsibility, emotional nurture, and problem resolution. Within this framing, endurance was being moralized and emotional needs were considered as secondary to family stability and social reputation. In this way, the sub-

theme shows that, through religious discourse and communal norms, endurance can be maintained but the issues of justice, reciprocity, and the wellbeing of women are not tackled.

A number of women stated that imams or elders stressed patience and family status, and very little attention was paid to the misbehaviour of husbands. One of the interviewees remembered one of the initial attempts to get help:

"We talked to an imam. He kept telling me to be patient and to make an attempt to make my husband happier... The experience during that session made me feel more caught up such as that the problem was that I lacked patience." (P 7)

This was the same hesitation expressed by another participant who wanted to make a call again:

"I worry that in case I open up too much to the religious leaders, they will advise me to be patient, and I would not receive some practical assistance. That is why I am afraid to contact you further." (P 5)

These passages explain how engagement with religious leaders might occasionally act as a process of restraint and not support. Religious counselling can sometimes cause complex interpersonal distress to be a moral need of feminine endurance. It may put the woman's spiritual inadequacy, rather than marital injustice, emotional neglect, or unmet rights, as the source of dissatisfaction. The participant's hesitation perpetuates this pattern by demonstrating the anticipatory impact of the advice: she anticipates it to be redundant and too unhelpful, which reduces help-seeking and further isolates women.

Many women talked about a certain taboo of revealing marital issues culturally. As shared by (P 8)

"In my society, much focus is given to the privacy of marital problems. That is why I am hesitant to share. I am much more concerned with gossip than real support." (P 8)

This quote shows that community norms and fear of social surveillance influence women coping through their discouragement of disclosure and help-seeking. The fact that the participant focuses on privacy is indicative of a cultural background in which marital dissatisfaction is often discussed within the family, rather than as an issue that falls under the category of support. Her emphasis on the fact that sharing will result in gossip and not caring implies that the community is less of a protective environment and more of a disciplinary environment that governs the speech and actions

of women through reputational threats. Consequently, women can be left alone in their feelings as they conceal the distress to avoid stigmatization and being impacted by the social effects.

Finally, this sub-theme shows that religious and community effects tended to influence coping by encouraging privacy, patience, and preservation of marriage, rather than emotional validation, accountability, and practical assistance. The experiences of the participants demonstrate that religious advice partially alleviated complex marital dissatisfaction to a burden of patience and satisfying the husband, which aggravated feelings of guilt and self-blame and confined women.

5.5.2 Proving the rights of women and putting them into practice.

This sub-theme records when religious leaders, teachers, or other community members with a strong faith and belief in Islam gave guidance that legitimized the Islamic rights of women and changed coping to a problem-oriented agentic coping. Unlike this advice that focused on patience alone, participants reported experiences of getting rights-based interpretations of Islam which acknowledged reciprocal duties in marriage, equity, and the avoidance of harm.

Exposure to more gender-conscious thinkers, particularly those women religious teachers, tended to change women's paths. P 3. was about a visiting female scholar who re-framed her position: *"According to her, Islam does not condone abuse, and that a woman can divorce in case she is abused. It was a teaching that altered all... the teaching that allowed me to defend myself and my children."* (P 3)

This quote shows how a rights-based religious direction can be used as a point of departure by turning faith into a source of validation and action. According to the participant, his interpretation included a direct connection between Islam and not suffering harm, and that women also had valid choices in religion, like getting a divorce when they are victimised. The statement of that teaching changed everything is the indication of a significant change in terms of meaning-making: what might have seemed a religious duty to bear is re-conceived as a religious duty to respect, preserve safety, and justice.

The other member had a mixed experience where one of the local scholars advised him to be patient and to demand justice at the same time:

"He reminded my husband mostly to be fair between his wives... In my case, the scholar also urged me to be patient... It was reassuring, but in some sense I felt that it was meant to be a pain that I would silently bear rather than discuss." (P 5)

This quote reflects the conflict that the participants were in when religious direction partially validated but still supported gendered endurance. On the one hand, the fact that the scholar reminds the wife that the husband needs to be fair among wives carries moral responsibility and can be felt as a soothing element, since the religious duty is not limited to women. Conversely, the subject observes that the guidance given to her was based on the concept of time i.e. patience, which, although comforting in the immediate, also asked her to be silent about her misery but to get through it.

Others approached teachers who doubted the cultural perversion of Islam on purpose. One of the participants talked about how she had actively learned about "actual Islam" with her husband to unravel it from the question of cultural Islam, and she concluded:

A good Muslim woman is well-balanced, intelligent and calculative. She defends her tranquillity, her demarcations and her spouse do not allow anyone to convince her that being turned into a doormat to her in laws is the way a good Muslim bahu should be. (P 4)

This quotation illustrates a justice-based, enabling religious discourse that proactively addresses culture-specific issues of female self-denial within the framework of marriage and extended family. Instead of assuming it to be pious to be quiet and endures many things, the speaker constructs the image of a good Muslim woman as balanced, tactical and self-defensive, with a particular focus on emotional health (guards her peace), limits, and responsibility.

These experiences indicate that religious leaders and societies can play a reinforcing role in negative coping (by sending one-sided messages about sabr and obedience) or support positive and justice-oriented coping by explicitly referring to the violence and supporting the rights of women.

6. Discussion

This paper examined the experiences of religiously practising married women and their coping mechanisms in marital dissatisfaction, along with how religious beliefs and practices influence the same. The results indicate that religion can play

both the roles of emotional support and framework which can affect the persistence of the marriage hardships and religious coping has been found to play a dual role (Pargament, 1997). Emotional loneliness in marriage was a common occurrence among participants who said that they felt neglected and unsupported. This is consistent with past studies suggesting that women in traditional family settings tend to be emotionally isolated because cultural demands prioritize conjugal cohesiveness over individual well-being (Whisman, 2001; Fincham & Beach, 2010). This emotional neglect is known to cause more psychological distress (Kiecolt-Glaser & Newton, 2001).

Religion became one of the major coping strategies. Religions like prayer, dependence on God, and meaning-making were comforting and assisted participants to overcome emotional pain. These results corroborate the literature that indicated that religious coping is positively correlated with positive adjustment to stress (Pargament et al., 2000). Even where there was no spousal support, faith provided hope and stability. Simultaneously, there were religious interpretations, restrictions, particularly when it comes to *sabr* (patience). The participants commonly defined patience as silent endurance that was supported by cultural and religious messages that discouraged confrontation or seeking of help. Religion is also thought to legitimize the suffering of women in marriage as religious teachings mediated by the patriarchal norms have been said to normalize this suffering (Ahmed, 1992; Ali, 2010) thereby constraining the perceived possibilities and postponing seeking of support.

Other participants have redefined *sabr* to mean emotional strength, self-control, and conscious choice, rather than enduring passively. This depicts the fact that religious coping is dynamic and capable of underpinning the agency and well-being of women (Bano & Kalmbach, 2012). Religious and family reaction was confused. Whereas others stressed patience as the way to go, others acknowledged the distress but offered little advice. The lack of coherent counselling can lead to the effects of confusion and more prolonged suffering, which supports the role of informed and sympathetic religious advice (Haddad, Smith, and Moore, 2006).

The same findings reinforce Religious Coping Theory by Pargament (1997), which indicates that

women's responses to marital dissatisfaction were influenced by the meaning they gave to their lives and the kind of religious coping they used. The dual pattern indicates the primary argument of the theory that religious coping may be protective and harmful at the same time in relation to whether it supports the secure and compassionate meaning-making or the punitive and restrictive meanings making. Nevertheless, in the Pakistani sociocultural environment, other variables served as critical moderators of religious coping outcomes, especially gender norms, joint-family pressures, and the influence of religious leaders and community discourse. On balance, the research proves that the explanatory role of Pargament's (1997) framework can be reinforced through the idea that coping is interpreted as an intrapersonal meaning system and a socially mediated process, which is why it needs to be examined in terms of contextual sensitivity of the way religion can influence women's agency, wellbeing and marriage decisions in Pakistan.

Altogether, these results highlight the significance of the religious coping study for culture and gendering. Religion does not exist independently of social norms, family expectations, and power relations but only shapes marital experiences. The findings affirm culturally competent approaches to counseling that incorporate religious values and authenticate the emotional needs and power of women (Worthington et al., 2011).

7. Conclusion

The paper examined the perceptions of religiously observant Pakistani Muslim women and their lived experiences of marital dissatisfaction, and how they employ the relational distress-religious coping strategies. The results show that religion is seen as a key framework of interpreting and addressing marital strain- it tends to serve as an emotional regulator, source of meaning and strength as opposed to a ritual. Meanwhile, coping was not empowering equally. These were aggravated by such sociocultural stressors as the demands of joint-family norms, privacy limitations, and the fear of societal gossip. The research paper adds to the Religious Coping Theory by Pargament (1997) by showing that both positive and negative religious coping processes run simultaneously even in marital situations. Notably, the results indicate that coping is not always the same: a general pattern of transitioning to a more justice-oriented faith was

reported by many of the women. Comprehensively, the results indicate that religion has a huge potential in helping women to be well and make decisions in troubled marriages, the way it will do so is based on the interpretation and social mediation of the religious messages. Marital and mental-health initiatives in Pakistan would thus need to be spiritually attentive and rights-conscious so as to uphold faith in women but foster emotional security, reciprocal marital accountability, and connect women to useful support networks that lessen isolation and stigma.

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